

Hair Bundle Mechanics Provides the Correct Phase Lead for Cochlear Amplification

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Abstract. The micromechanics of cochlear amplification remains to be understood. There are multiple theories about how outer hair cell motility is coupled to its surrounding organ of Corti that might result in motion amplification. Tectorial membrane resonance has been hypothesized and used in cochlear models with some success. However, experimental evidence for tectorial membrane resonance is lacking leading to the reticular lamina resonance hypothesis, which also lacks experimental evidence. This paper proposes a new hypothesis that uses a tuned feedback loop instead of resonance. Mechano-electrical transduction (MET) current adaptation behaves like a high-pass filter with phase lead that compensates for phase lag introduced by outer hair cell motility and membrane capacitance in the feedback path and enables cycle-by-cycle motion amplification. We demonstrate this in a finite element slice model of the gerbil cochlea mid-frequency region with pressure input that drives the organ of Corti. Incorporation of a hair bundle high-pass filter with phase lead generates significant motion gain of the reticular lamina and basilar membrane in the slice model relative to the passive case. Thus, the phase lead required for cochlear motion amplification is hypothesized to be neither in the tectorial membrane, or the reticular lamina, but in between in hair bundle mechanics, which does have significant experimental support.

INTRODUCTION

The organ of Corti has a very complex structure which moves in response to sounds. Outer hair cell (OHC) motility is thought to improve the sensitivity and frequency selectivity of hearing by amplifying frequency dependent motions in the cochlea. Sound-induced transverse motion of the basilar membrane (BM) leads to radial shearing between the tectorial membrane (TM) and reticular lamina (RL). The resulting deflection of hair bundles (HBs) on top of the OHCs opens mechano-electrical transduction (MET) channels. The potential difference between scala media and the OHC intracellular holding potential drives MET currents through the opened channels into the cells (reviewed in [1]). Adaptation partly closes MET channels for low frequency stimuli, reducing the current [2]. The MET currents change receptor potentials and affect prestin molecules at the OHC cell walls that generate forces which lead to subsequent OHC contraction or elongation (e.g., [3]). These length changes increase BM and RL motion due to mechanical coupling to the OHCs and improve sensitivity of hearing. This is a positive feedback loop (Fig. 1) with frequency-dependent loop gain [4]. The resulting motion highly depends on the phase of the generated forces which determines whether the feedback is positive or negative.

Lots of different models examine the complicated micromechanics of the active cochlea [5], [6], [7]. These models scale OHC force linearly with basilar membrane (BM) pressure or the force or displacement angle of the HB with zero phase lag [5], [6], [7]. This reduces the complexity of the described feedback loop considerably but is an oversimplification. Building a model of the entire cochlea requires significant anatomical reductions because of limitations in computational power. This restricts the amount of visible detail, which is needed to analyze micromechanics. One way around this is the use of a finite element (FE) modeling approach for a slice of the cochlea, which represents a detailed cut through the cochlea. It uses Floquet boundary conditions at the faces of the slice which

approximate a traveling wave [8]. This model was passive and could not be used to study the details of active sound amplification in living animals. Active OHCs were added to the passive model to make this possible.

FIGURE 1. Cochlear motion amplification model with feedback. The full model is shown on the left and HB displacement to OHC force production details are shown on the right. A pressure P_{stim} in the scala tympani is the input of the FE model leading to BM pressure difference, BM displacement, RL and TM shear motion, and radial HB displacement x_{hb} . MET channels translate this to a current I_{MET} that flows into the cell. OHC impedance leads to a change in receptor potential V_{RP} , which makes prestin molecules in the OHC wall generate an OHC force F_{OHC} producing pressure at BM, closing the feedback loop.

METHODS

Cochlear feedback mechanics was analyzed using FE modeling. A passive slice model [8] was modified to incorporate bundle mechanics and active OHCs. A cross-sectional slice of the middle turn of the gerbil cochlea which is 20 μm thick was modeled with 3 OHCs, one per row. It uses a Floquet boundary condition at the two longitudinal surfaces such that it approximates a wave with wavelength that varies with frequency. The key advantage of this approach is that it allows for incorporation of the rich detailed structure of the organ of Corti with reasonable computation time. The passive model was calibrated to match measured data for 80 dB SPL input [9].

To make this model active, various OHC mechanics were incorporated. Each step introduces frequency-dependent amplitudes and phases (Fig. 1), discussed below.

MET Model

HB radial displacement x_{hb} leads to an MET current I_{MET} flowing into the OHC. This can be simulated by modifying a simplified MET model by Rabbitt et al. [10], which now includes a MET fast adaptation current:

$$\frac{dI_{MET}}{dt} + \frac{1}{\tau_T} I_{MET} = G_T \left(A \frac{dx_{hb}}{dt} + B x_{hb} \right). \quad (1)$$

Here, τ_T is the channel's adaptation time constant, G_T is the transduction current gain. A and B are scaling factors defining the residual current of the MET channel step response. The step input displacement and resulting response current are shown in Fig. 2a. A 1 μm HB displacement first leads to a current spike of -1 nA which then adapts and reaches a steady state current of -3.9 pA. The addition of the term Bx_{hb} prevents the current from returning to zero and is thus the adaptation current which can be arbitrarily set to any value.

Time domain Eq. (1) can be translated to the frequency domain and simplified as follows:

$$I_{MET}(\omega) = G_T \frac{i\omega A\tau_T + B\tau_T}{1 + i\omega\tau_T} \cdot x_{hb}, \quad (2)$$

using $\omega = 2\pi f$ with frequency f .

This model leads to the frequency response shown in Fig. 2b, first column. The filter behaves nearly like an electrical high-pass filter, but with a resistor in parallel with capacitance (leaky capacitor) that sets the phase to zero and the magnitude to a constant value, as frequency asymptotically decreases to zero.

OHC Membrane Model

The MET current I_{MET} was used to compute the receptor potential V_{RP} using an OHC impedance model with a low-pass filter response having an experimentally confirmed cut-off frequency of 3 kHz [11]:

$$V_{RP}(\omega) = \frac{R_m}{1 + i\omega C_m R_m} \cdot I_{MET}. \quad (3)$$

R_m and C_m are OHC membrane resistance and capacitance. The low-pass frequency response is presented in Fig. 2b, second column.

OHC Force Model

The receptor potential V_{RP} was used to calculate the generated force F_{OHC} . A two-state prestin model was used to simulate prestin and OHC physiology [3]. To achieve this, the motile element displacement y needed to be computed. It represents the displacement of all prestin molecules combined in the mechanical model:

$$y(\omega) = -\frac{\beta a q k_2 \bar{P}_{\pm} N}{1 + i\omega/\omega_g} \cdot \frac{1}{G_2(\omega) + k_2} \cdot V_{RP}, \quad (4)$$

with

$$G_2(\omega) = \frac{k_1^2}{k_0 + k_1 + i\omega\eta_0} - (k_1 + k_2 + i\omega\eta_2). \quad (5)$$

$\beta = 1/(k_B T)$ combines Boltzmann-constant k_B and temperature T and a is the unit length change on conformational change of an individual prestin molecule. q is the charge transferred across the membrane when a prestin molecule changes its state and there are N motors in an OHC. k_0, k_1, k_2, η_0 and η_2 are stiffness and damping coefficients modeling the mechanics of the OHC and its environment. $\bar{P}_{\pm} = \bar{P}_1(1 - \bar{P}_1)$, with \bar{P}_1 being the probability of prestin being in its shortened state at 0 Hz frequency, ω_g is the roll-off frequency due to the limited speed of prestin.

The force F_{OHC} was computed via:

$$F_{OHC}(\omega) = y(\omega) \cdot G_2(\omega). \quad (6)$$

The resulting 2nd order low-pass OHC force response is shown in Fig. 2b, third column.

Full OHC Model

The three transfer functions presented in Eqs. (2), (3) and (6) were chained to compute the force F_{OHC} that an OHC generates in response to a radial HB displacement x_{hb} . This leads to the total frequency response shown in Fig. 2b, fourth column. The total filter (F_{OHC}/x_{hb}) response is band-pass-like with a total accumulated phase at BF at 1.8 kHz that has a phase lead of 0.063 cycles, which is close to 0 cycles.

This OHC force production model was plugged into the passive FE model mechanics. It was applied to each OHC individually, to the top and bottom edges of the cylindrical OHCs with opposite forces. This allows for the OHCs to contract and elongate, depending on the sign of the applied force.

The model was solved in the frequency domain using COMSOL Multiphysics version 6.2 (COMSOL AB, Stockholm, Sweden) with a relatively low level $P_{stim}=50$ dB SPL applied in the scala tympani (Fig. 1).

FIGURE 2. Components of the OHC model from bundle displacement to MET current as a function of time (a) and the chain of events leading to force production as a function of frequency (b). a): Left: HB displacement step input (μm) and right: MET current response (nA). b): Top: amplitudes, bottom: phases. Left to right: MET adaptation model (frequency domain of (a) right) (A/m), OHC impedance model (V/A), OHC force model (N/V) and total displacement to force (F_{OHC}/x_{hb}) production model (N/m).

RESULTS

Applying a 50 dB SPL input pressure at different frequencies led to the transverse BM and RL displacements shown in Fig. 3. In the passive model, RL and BM showed the same displacement that stayed relatively constant between 0.1 kHz and 1.6 kHz before decreasing rapidly, consistent with scaled measurements made at similar locations with 80 dB SPL ear canal input [9].

With all three model stages of the OHC included, there was significant increase in the motion of BM and RL starting from 0.1 kHz, reaching a peak at the active BF of 1.8 kHz and then decreasing. RL displacement was generally higher than BM displacement and BM amplification was narrower, starting near the BF at about 1.6 kHz. Both RL and BM displacement dropped quickly when the frequency was higher than BF and approached passive values.

Substituting the MET adaptation model with a constant scaling factor (effectively bypassing it) led to RL and BM transverse displacements that were smaller than in the passive case (Fig. 3, solid black line).

The phases of transverse displacement matched passive phases at low frequencies, but they decreased more slowly than in the passive case. Between 1750 Hz and 1850 Hz, there was a jump in phase by about 0.4 cycles. RL and BM always showed very similar phases, but they differed more and more with frequency until the rapid phase changes around BF made them match again. Not having an MET adaptation model led to an RL phase that led more and more compared to the passive model. There was no jump in phase at BF.

FIGURE 3. BM and RL frequency responses for passive and active models. Magnitude (left) and phase (right). Transverse displacements of RL (blue) and BM (orange). Passive model outputs are shown in dashed gray (RL and BM motions were the same). RL motion when no MET adaptation was included is plotted in solid black.

DISCUSSION

Forward transduction (sensing of motion) and reverse transduction (feedback of force) were conceptualized previously as part of a negative feedback loop [4]. We developed such a formulation using an anatomically based finite element model. The presented model shows high amplification of RL and BM transverse displacement near BF, but also some gain at lower frequencies. This was achieved by cycle-by-cycle amplification using a phase lead representing MET adaptation. It compensates for the phase lags introduced at other steps of the feedback loop. Previous models [12], [13] assumed resonances of TM to explain amplification at BF. Recent OCT based measurements could not find any empirical evidence for TM resonance, however [14], [15]. An alternate idea for RL resonance was also proposed but the evidence for that is also lacking [15]. While the details need to be further developed, the MET phase lead model offers a proof of concept for a possible new mechanism to achieve cycle-by-cycle amplification using physiology based OHC bundle mechanics and somatic motility.

Figures 3 show that phase lead introduced by HB MET mechanics was necessary to achieve amplification in this model (Fig. 1). A standard model for MET bundle mechanics ($B=0$, in Eq. 1) has a high-pass-like frequency response that introduces a 0.25 cycle phase lead at low frequencies that decreases to 0 cycles well beyond the corner frequency [10]. With such a model, one can achieve significant RL and BM gain near the BF of about 1.8 kHz. This was achieved by choosing MET high-pass filter parameters such that the phase of the F_{OHC}/x_{hb} was close to 0 cycles near BF leading to amplification. But there was little to no gain for frequencies lower than $\frac{1}{2}$ -octave below the BF (not shown). It has been shown that there is significant gain and compression in both BM and RL well below the mid-frequency BF region of ~ 2 kHz in gerbil [16], [9]. Our initial model did not provide gain at the lowest frequencies and we further explored this.

We surmised that driving the HB phase towards 0 cycles at the lower frequencies would also lead to gain at those frequencies. Towards this, we used the equivalent of an electrical leaky capacitance, where a parallel resistor bypasses the capacitance at low frequencies (implemented with Bx_{hb} on the right-hand side in Eq. (1)), driving the phase towards zero cycles (Fig. 2b, first column). This resistor can be thought of as representing the sub tectorial space which dampens motion, whereas the capacitance represents the HB stiffness including tip-link stiffness. The sub tectorial space is thought to be dominated by a viscous boundary layer ([17], [18]) proportional to $1/\sqrt{f}$ and thus

increases with decreasing frequency (e.g., [19]). This additional resistor was required because we represented the rows of HBs as a single row without the second or third row connected by tip links that would otherwise go through adaptation. The representation of this viscous component in Eq. (1) leads to adaptation-like bundle mechanics, pulling the low frequency phase towards zero. This adaptation is also consistent with experimental data, where the step response current does not decrease to zero after the initial fast current due to a fast adaptation (Fig. 2a) [2]. There is also slow adaptation on timescales that are slow compared to fast adaptation but presently not included [2].

The phase difference between RL and BM was expected to be less than 0.5 cycles at low frequencies [9]. In the model, there was some phase difference between RL and BM but this could be improved. Further changes to the HB adaption model parameters and their cut-off frequencies may be able to increase low frequency phase differences between RL and BM. Including this fast adaptation in the MET bundle mechanics increased the gain magnitude in RL and BM relative to the passive model providing proof of concept that MET hair bundle adaptation provides the necessary phase lead that counters the phase lag due to somatic motility resulting in cochlear amplification.

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REFERENCES

- [1] D. Ó Maoiléidigh and A. J. Ricci, “A Bundle of Mechanisms: Inner-Ear Hair-Cell Mechanotransduction,” *Trends Neurosci.*, vol. 42, no. 3, pp. 221–236, Mar. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.tins.2018.12.006.
- [2] A. J. Ricci, H. J. Kennedy, A. C. Crawford, and R. Fettiplace, “The Transduction Channel Filter in Auditory Hair Cells,” *J. Neurosci.*, vol. 25, no. 34, pp. 7831–7839, Aug. 2005, doi: 10.1523/JNEUROSCI.1127-05.2005.
- [3] J. Santos-Sacchi, K. H. Iwasa, and W. Tan, “Outer hair cell electromotility is low-pass filtered relative to the molecular conformational changes that produce nonlinear capacitance,” *J. Gen. Physiol.*, vol. 151, no. 12, pp. 1369–1385, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.1085/jgp.201812280.
- [4] A. E. Hubbard and D. C. Mountain, “Haircell forward and reverse transduction: Differential suppression and enhancement,” *Hear. Res.*, vol. 43, no. 2, pp. 269–272, Jan. 1990, doi: 10.1016/0378-5955(90)90234-G.
- [5] A. Altoè and C. A. Spera, “Nonlinear cochlear mechanics without direct vibration-amplification feedback,” *Phys. Rev. Res.*, vol. 2, no. 1, p. 013218, Feb. 2020, doi: 10.1103/PhysRevResearch.2.013218.
- [6] H. Motallebzadeh, J. A. M. Soons, and S. Puria, “Cochlear amplification and tuning depend on the cellular arrangement within the organ of Corti,” *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*, vol. 115, no. 22, pp. 5762–5767, May 2018, doi: 10.1073/pnas.1720979115.
- [7] G. Samaras, H. Wen, and J. Meaud, “Broad nonlinearity in reticular lamina vibrations requires compliant organ of Corti structures,” *Biophys. J.*, vol. 122, no. 5, pp. 880–891, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.bpj.2023.01.029.
- [8] A. Tubelli, H. Motallebzadeh, J. J. Guinan, and S. Puria, “A Cochlea-Slice Model using Floquet Boundary Conditions shows Global Tuning,” Nov. 02, 2022, *bioRxiv*. doi: 10.1101/2022.10.31.514521.
- [9] S. W. F. Meenderink, X. Lin, B. H. Park, and W. Dong, “Sound Induced Vibrations Deform the Organ of Corti Complex in the Low-Frequency Apical Region of the Gerbil Cochlea for Normal Hearing,” *J. Assoc. Res. Otolaryngol.*, vol. 23, no. 5, pp. 579–591, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.1007/s10162-022-00856-0.
- [10] R. D. Rabbitt, S. Clifford, K. D. Breneman, B. Farrell, and W. E. Brownell, “Power Efficiency of Outer Hair Cell Somatic Electromotility,” *PLoS Comput. Biol.*, vol. 5, no. 7, p. e1000444, Jul. 2009, doi: 10.1371/journal.pcbi.1000444.
- [11] A. Vavakou, N. P. Cooper, and M. van der Heijden, “The frequency limit of outer hair cell motility measured in vivo,” *eLife*, vol. 8, p. e47667, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.7554/eLife.47667.
- [12] R. Nobili, F. Mammano, and J. Ashmore, “How well do we understand the cochlea?,” *Trends Neurosci.*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 159–167, Apr. 1998, doi: 10.1016/S0166-2236(97)01192-2.
- [13] A. Sasmal and K. Grosh, “Unified cochlear model for low- and high-frequency mammalian hearing,” *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*, vol. 116, no. 28, pp. 13983–13988, Jul. 2019, doi: 10.1073/pnas.1900695116.
- [14] J. J. Guinan, “The interplay of organ-of-Corti vibrational modes, not tectorial- membrane resonance, sets outer-hair-cell stereocilia phase to produce cochlear amplification,” *Hear. Res.*, vol. 395, p. 108040, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.heares.2020.108040.
- [15] J. B. Dewey, A. Xia, U. Müller, I. A. Belyantseva, B. E. Applegate, and J. S. Oghalai, “Mammalian

Auditory Hair Cell Bundle Stiffness Affects Frequency Tuning by Increasing Coupling along the Length of the Cochlea,” *Cell Rep.*, vol. 23, no. 10, pp. 2915–2927, Jun. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.celrep.2018.05.024.

[16] N. H. Cho, J. J. Guinan, and S. Puria, “Radial Motion within the Organ of Corti of the Gerbil Mid-Frequency Region Using High-Resolution Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) Vibrometry,” presented at the Association for Research in Otolaryngology, Orlando, FL, Feb. 2023.

[17] J. Allen, “Cochlear micromechanics—A physical model of transduction,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, vol. 68, pp. 1660–70, Jan. 1981, doi: 10.1121/1.385198.

[18] S. Prodanovic, S. Gracewski, and J.-H. Nam, “Power Dissipation in the Subtectorial Space of the Mammalian Cochlea Is Modulated by Inner Hair Cell Stereocilia,” *Biophys. J.*, vol. 108, no. 3, pp. 479–488, Feb. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.bpj.2014.12.027.

[19] S. Puria and J. B. Allen, “A parametric study of cochlear input impedance,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, vol. 89, no. 1, pp. 287–309, Jan. 1991, doi: 10.1121/1.400675.

COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Varun Goyal]: Hi Julius and Dr. Puria,

The paper thoroughly describes its contents, particularly your model, which presents an interesting idea with proof that HB motion could lead to cochlear amplification. I'm excited to see if it can be demonstrated experimentally. Here are some questions that have sparked my curiosity:

1. In paragraph 1, there is a discussion on positive or negative feedback. Is positive feedback defined when sensitivity improves? And so the negative feedback is when the phase is such that it reduces the hearing sensitivity?
2. The MET model description mentions that the current's adapted value can be set arbitrarily. My question is: In the presented results, is the adaptation current obtained from experimental estimates in gerbils? If not, how do you decide on a specific value? The change is about 99% (from 1000 pA peak to 3.9 pA). Is that something seen in experiments? I understand that slow adaptation is not included yet in the model.
3. Question about \bar{P}_{\pm} term in Eq 4. Is this probability, in general, a function of frequency? If so, are you linearizing this model about the 0 Hz frequency?
4. Just curious about degrees-of-freedom in the model: Each cross-section has 3 OHCs. How many such cross-sections are there in the FE model? More precisely, how many feedback loops are there in the global model?
5. The passive model was calibrated to 80 dB experimental responses. Is the 50 dB input to the BM (P_{stim} in the model, I assume) similar to the 80 dB ear canal input? What is an approximate transmission factor there?
6. Can you explain the differences between the passive model (Fig 3 dashed lines) and the "RL without adaptation" model (Fig 3 solid black lines)? Building on that, why is the response lower in the passive model?
7. What was the adaptation time constant value set in the presented results? Did you obtain it from experimental estimates? This question adds to my previous question about the arbitrariness of the adaptation magnitude.

These are mostly the curious questions that I have. Really interesting work!

Best,

Varun

[Julius Kraut]:

1. Positive feedback means that the feedback term amplifies the effects of the input on the system. This increases overall displacements in response to a sound stimulus which increases hearing sensitivity. Negative feedback would counteract the stimulus and reduce motion.
2. The step response of the MET current is shown in figure 2, top row. The current spike down to -1 nA is similar to experimental results ([2]). [2] also shows that the adaptation current depends on the stimulus level, the lower the stimulus, the closer the current returns to 0. The 99% change in the model that was presented may be an overestimation, but it is not completely unrealistic. Changing the adaptation current significantly affects the frequency response of the MET high-pass filter. Increasing the adaptation current is possible but requires changes to the other models to keep the gain of the full model high. There is room for improvement in all three model filters, the presented model is a proof of concept, however, that MET adaptation may be able to set the phase of the feedback path to amplify motion in the cochlea.
3. \bar{P}_{\pm} is frequency-independent, it is related to the DC component of the probability in which state the prestin molecules are at a given receptor potential.
4. The slice only includes one OHC per row, three in total. Each cell possesses its own OHC model from HB displacement to force production. Each of the three feedback loops uses the same parameters, the only differences are geometry-related. The Floquet boundary condition replicates this slice, and therefore the three OHCs are repeated longitudinally in both directions.
5. [9] measured passive BM displacements for 80 dB SPL stimuli in gerbils at a location that is similar to the slice model. They also captured motion of the active cochlea in the same animal at different levels, at 50 dB SPL amongst others. For this reason, a stimulus of 50 dB SPL was used to allow for a comparison between the active model results and experimental data. Passive BM displacements were reduced by 30 dB SPL to approximate passive BM motion at 50 dB SPL. The model did not include a middle ear which affected the input pressures of the model. [8], supplementary information showed the input pressures after calibration at 80 dB SPL (Fig. 4).

FIGURE 4. Differential pressure between scala tympani and scala vestibuli in a model of the full cochlea (dashed) and the slice model (blue). Magnitudes (top) and phases (bottom) plotted against frequency.

6. The "RL without adaptation model" used the same OHC membrane and force model as the active full model. The only difference between the two models was that the MET adaptation high-pass filter was substituted for a constant factor in the "RL without adaptation model". This value had the identical absolute value of the MET adaptation model in the full model at BF but did not introduce any phase. This change in phase led to negative feedback at BF. The force generated by the OHCs dampened BM motion which resulted in values lower than in the passive model where no active force was present.
7. The adaptation time constant was 0.5 μ s. This value was chosen to maximize motion using the given OHC membrane and force model. This value is about two orders of magnitude too fast when compared to experimental data (e.g. [2]). Modifications to the phases introduced by the membrane and force model will allow for the use of more realistic time constants in the future.

[Dzmitry Vaido]: Hello Julius and Sunil, thank you for this exciting work. It is interesting to see how combining a passive cochlea with active outer hair cells fits the experimental observations. I was wondering what numerical values you used for your parameters, did you take them all from previous experiments and fits or did you vary any of them as free parameters?

[Julius Kraut]: The parameters for each model were chosen to match experimental data as good as possible and are shown in Table 1. Some of these parameters could be modified to be more realistic. The present work is a proof of concept for a new idea that MET adaptation could introduce the phase lead that is required for amplification of motion in the cochlea.

1. For the OHC force model, parameters and equations were provided by [3]. These parameters were able to match electromotility and nonlinear capacitance measurements in low-frequency guinea pig OHCs. This defined the cut-off frequency and phase of the model, the absolute values could be scaled by a free parameter. The parameters were sufficient for this proof of concept but could be improved to better resemble gerbil data.
2. For the OHC membrane model, the cut-off frequency of the low-pass filter was set to 3 kHz which defined the phase of the model ([11]). The amplitude was a free parameter.
3. For the MET adaptation model, the current spike of the step response approximately matched experimental data. The rest of the filter was assumed to have free parameters that were set up to maximize gain with respect to the parameters that were chosen for the other models.

Variable	Definition	Value
Modified MET Adaptation Model		
τ_T	Adaptation time constant	0.5 μ s
G_T	Transduction current gain	1.812 mA/m
A	Peak current scaling factor	0.55
B	Adaptation current scaling factor	1×10^3 1/s
Simple OHC Membrane Model		
R_m	OHC Membrane Resistance	210.7 G Ω
C_m	OHC Membrane Capacitance	0.2563 fF
OHC Force Model		
T	Temperature	310 K
\bar{k}	Transition rate due to energy barrier between states	12 kHz
V_0	Holding potential	-45.8 mV
$V_{1/2}$	Half-point voltage of transition	-55 mV
q	Charge transferred across cell membrane by prestin	0.7e
e	Electron charge	-1.602×10^{-19} C
k_1	Stiffness	50 mN/m
k_2	Stiffness	$1.31 \cdot k_1$
k_0	Stiffness	$3.82 \cdot k_2$
η_0	Damping coefficient	270 μ g/s
η_2	Damping coefficient	$0.479 \cdot \eta_0$
N	Number of prestin molecules	70×10^6
a	Unit length change on conformational change	-0.1 pm

TABLE 1. Model parameters that maximized the gain of the active slice model.